

Rethinking East-West relations: Rabindranath, Visva-Bharati and European Orientalist scholars

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Abstract

Rabindranath Tagore (1861-1941) gained global recognition and fame after the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1913. Feted as a philosopher-sage there was considerable interest in his educational philosophy for children since he had set up an ashram in the school in Santiniketan in 1901.

In 1916, while travelling in the US and Japan Rabindranath began to think of ways of creating in Santiniketan an international centre devoted to the pursuit of knowledge systems and culture that could bring in the best minds of the East and West. He later gave it the name Visva-Bharati, the world centre of learning and its motto was *yatra visvam bhabyeeknidam* which translates as 'where the world makes its home in a nest.'

Among the European scholars he invited to Visva-Bharati were the Orientalist Sylvain Levi (1863-1935) a professor at the University of Sorbonne, the Jewish Austrian Morris Winternitz (1863-1937) and his student Vincent Lesney, the Norwegian Sten Konow (1867-1948), the Italians Carlo Formici (1871-1943) and Guiseppe Tucci (1895-1984). Though they did not stay for long there were fruitful exchanges with Indian scholars who studied Sanskrit, Pali, Prakrit, Chinese and Tibetan. Thus Visva-Bharati became an important site of Asian comparative studies.

The invitation to European Orientalists to Visva-Bharati was to initiate an exchange of scholars between the Asia and Europe. For the first time since colonial modernity, Westerners had come at the behest of an Indian to be part of his project of creating a world centre of learning and culture. This in itself over-turned the hegemonic model in which the West determined the production of knowledge and modes of its dissemination. This essay is part of a book titled *Tagore's University (1921-1961)* to be published by Permanent Black, New Delhi/Ranikhet (Forthcoming).

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A poet, an award and a dream

The award of the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1913, for the English

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Gitanjali, gave global recognition to Rabindranath Tagore (1861-1941) not only as a world-poet but also as a philosopher-sage and a public intellectual. Feted by educated Europeans, free from racist prejudices, Rabindranath travelled widely and spoke, among other subjects, of his school which he had set up twelve years ago in a small sleepy town which had been named Santiniketan (literally abode of peace) by his father who had conceived it as an ashram or retreat for those belonging to Brahma faith. Rabindranath's ashram school was modelled on the pedagogical principle that lay at the heart of the ancient Indian *tapovana* or forest hermitages. The *tapovana* was where young male pupils lived with the great sages and learnt from them and this idea appealed to Rabindranath who gave it a central position in his philosophy of education. He regarded it as a "vital centre" of the "social body" which permeated all aspects of living.¹ This intimate relation between human beings and the universe, Rabindranath argued, was crucial especially during childhood since it was in the early years that the child acquired his/her first lessons from nature. In contemporary colonial schools, built in crowded and noisy cities of brick and mortar, the student was confined within the four walls of a classroom, subjected to rote learning and a rigorous discipline and punish regime. This virtually stifled the natural curiosities in the learner.² The ideal institution therefore had to be located away from the city "in solitude, under the open sky, amidst wild fields, trees and plants."³ The Santiniketan ashram provided such a space. He was thus a poet whose pedagogy and philosophy had a firm grounding, in a real place, in a community of teachers and pupils. Suffused with utopian principles the Santiniketan ashram was a world unto itself.

Between 1913 and 1916 Rabindranath began to think of creating in Santiniketan a centre devoted to the pursuit of knowledge systems that could bring in the best minds of the East and West. He hoped to garner support, both intellectual and financial for his institution. Asserting his belief in collaboration with the West was not an easy

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task at a time when the country was swept by the growing tide of nationalism spearheaded by Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi (1869-1948), whose anti-racist satyagraha programme in South Africa, focusing on the plight of indentured Indian labour, Rabindranath had endorsed wholeheartedly.⁴ He had facilitated Gandhi's passage to India from South Africa, first by hosting the boys of Phoenix school in the Santiniketan ashram and later by organizing a warm ceremonial welcome to Mohandas Gandhi in Santiniketan in 1915. In the intervening years – 1916-1919, Gandhi embarked on his political career in India and emerged as the charismatic leader of the Congress who could mobilize the masses for the cause of nationalism and anti-colonial protests. During the same period, Rabindranath's political ideas evolved in ways that set him apart not only from Gandhi but from many other political leaders.

Central to this evolution was Rabindranath's scathing critique of the concept of nation and nationalism as the root of malaise plaguing the world at large. Deeply disturbed as he was by World War I, Rabindranath had analyzed the war among nations as having its basis in the ideology of nationalism. As a result, he felt morally and intellectually compelled to denounce nationalism as a menace; in his reading nationalism was a necessity for capitalism and imperialism. He developed these ideas in a series of lectures, delivered in Japan and the US in 1916; this was also the time that he first articulated his idea of *Visva-Bharati*. He was firm in his conviction that this equation of conflict and power had to be discarded in favour of a philosophy and praxis of co-operation and exchange among Europe and Asia, an idea that he had begun developing in his lectures⁵ delivered in 1916 during his tour in Japan and the US. A recurrent theme of the nationalism essays is that it is inimical to the notion of what it means to be human; nation is anti-human.

In all three lectures, Rabindranath makes a plea to create an antidote to the lethal poison of nationalism: viz. a restoration of man to his natural surroundings, to the fullness of communal life, with all its living association of beauty, love and social obligations. A true

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valuation of human, Rabindranath asserts, is by a return to the universal. Any attempt to stop humankind and civilization from hurtling into extinction required that an effort be made to foster an inspiring atmosphere of creative activity where the mind of man would find its proper nurturing. It is precisely in this context that it is important to locate Rabindranath's thinking about Visva-Bharati. In a letter dated 11 October 1916, from Los Angeles, which he wrote to his son Rathindranath Tagore contains the first succinct account of his wish to turn the educational institution in Santiniketan into a link/connection between the country and the larger world.⁶ He hoped this could be achieved by establishing a centre for the study of humanity that belonged to all races. He wrote of his belief that the time for narrow chauvinism was coming to an end, and it was in the open fields of Bolpur that he hoped to lay the foundation of the grand meeting place or what he called the "mahamilanyajna" for all of human-kind.⁷ This was an audacious dream and only a visionary poet-philosopher who had pondered deeply about a world historical crisis of humanity could have dared think along these lines. Visva-Bharati was to be a centre 'where the intellect and cultures of all the Eastern and Western countries would be brought together.'⁸

Visva-Bharati or the making of world centre of learning in Santiniketan

It was this very need to embrace the world, to provide a hospitable habitation for humanity devoted to learning and culture, which informed the project of Visva-Bharati. It is significant that the Sanskrit phrase, *yatra visvam bhabyeeknidam* which translates as 'where the world makes its home in a nest' was chosen as a motto of Visva-Bharati and not the ashram school though the scholar Vidushekhar Bhattacharya, who is credited with having suggested this to Rabindranath, was a member of the ashram from its early days.

Two scholars who served as a bridge between the school and the centre of higher learning were Vidushekhar Bhattacharya (1878-1958) and Kshitimohan Sen (1880-1960). They were

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contemporaries who had studied Sanskrit in Benaras, one of the most reputed seats of traditional learning. Initially they were appointed to teach Sanskrit to the boys in the *brahmacharyashram* but their roles went beyond school pedagogy. Vidushekhar learned Chinese and then Tibetan at the behest of Rabindranath and Kshitimohan, who had an interest in the medieval Bhakti poetry, was inspired by the founder of the ashram school to take up his work of compiling the verses of Kabir. Both these Pandits introduced certain formal 'traditional Indian' ritualistic elements to the academic ceremonies of the institution; these included the decoration of the site, the chanting of Vedic hymns, the uttering of *swasti-vachan* or blessings to the students during convocation, the use of flowers and sandal-paste to welcome guests. Rabindranath approved of the aesthetics of these ceremonies which imbued the institution with an aura of ancient heritage.⁹ Rabindranath had very high regard of the scholarship of both Kshitimohan and Vidushekhar and was convinced that they were eminently suited to give shape to the research programme and guide the students who came to pursue their research interests in various aspects of Indological and Asiatic studies. Visva-Bharati was imagined as a world centre of learning that would break the silence and the insularity of the systems of higher learning that existed in India from pre-colonial times. It was necessary for knowledge systems of the East and West to be in a meaningful dialogue. This was not the West which flexed its muscles through mechanisms of power and control, not the West which was a conglomerate of colonialist, capitalist and fascist enterprises. An optimist till his last breath, Rabindranath valued Europe's educational and cultural institutions and those individuals who actively pursued the path of learning without linking it to questions of power and domination.

The ideal named Visva-Bharati

The first lecture in which Rabindranath elucidated the idea of Visva-Bharati was delivered on the occasion of its foundation on 22

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December 1918, and published in the *Santiniketan Patrika* in 1919. In his characteristic rhetorical flourish he spoke about the idea of a festive celebration of knowledge in the world of man, one which is akin to the Diwali or festival of lights. Such a festival could be successful only when each country – Rabindranath uses the word *jati* which ordinarily translates as race but would be erroneous in this context, can keep its own special lamp of learning burning brightly.¹⁰ Implicit in this metaphor is the regret that Bharatbarsha has not tended its own flame of knowledge and learning. Typically, Rabindranath posits that there was a time when the country was ‘capable of asserting its powers of intellect because there was unity and integrity of her mind.’ In the present time, ‘the mind of the country ‘lies divided and dissolute among Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, Sikhs, Muslims and Christians. In its present dissipated state, the country can neither give nor accept anything meaningful.’¹¹

It was thus crucial to seek an alternative. Rabindranath made three propositions concerning the ideal path that a centre of higher education in the country should try to pursue. The first was to create a union of the ‘Vedic, Puranic, Buddhist, Jain, Christian and Islamic’ knowledges, because the ‘mind of Bharatbarsha’, had in the past, been flowing along these streams. It was only by establishing a connection with these aspects of its past could the country hope to regain its lost ‘wealth of mind.’¹² The second proposition was that the primary aim of higher education should be production of knowledge; teaching ought to be secondary. Thus a true centre of higher education could only be founded on the ‘banks of the fountain of knowledge,’ created by bringing together eminent scholars whose minds are immersed in the pursuit of creative learning.¹³ In other words research would constitute the core of Visva-Bharati dedicated to the pursuit of knowledge. And finally there would have to be a meaningful relation between institutions of higher education and the general life of the country. Colonial education has been limited to producing, clerks, deputy magistrates, lawyers and doctors, those

professions that benefit the middle classes alone. The real aim of higher education should be the establishment of an intimate connection between its institution and its immediate surroundings, allow its researches in economics, agriculture and health to effect a change in the lives and livelihoods of ordinary rural people.¹⁴ Rabindranath ended his address with his proposal that an institution created with such ideals was to be named Visva-Bharati.¹⁵

Though the idea of Visva-Bharati was articulated by the poet-philosopher in December 1918, it was not till July 1919, that the centre for learning and culture became fully functional and students began to enroll for research oriented work under Vidushekhar Sashtri and Kshitmohan Sen. The artists Nandalal Bose and his cousin Surendranath Kar, had joined Kala-Bhavana, the school of fine arts and music; the Hindusthani Classical singers Bhimrao Sashtri and Nakuleshwar Misra had arrived earlier. By 1920, Rabindranath who was travelling in Europe began to meet European Orientalists, and impress upon them to come to Visva-Bharati.

Seeking scholars from Europe for Visva-Bharati

In August 1920 Rabindranath Tagore and his entourage stayed in a beautiful guest house in Autour du Monde – in the outskirts of Paris, as guests of the Jewish philanthropist Alfred Kahn (1860-1940). A substantial amount of the immense wealth, which Kahn had amassed as a banker, was spent generously in providing bursaries at the Autour du Monde for scholars, artists, scientists. An exact contemporary of Rabindranath, Kahn shared the Nobel Laureate's faith that developing close relationships among societies and cultures across the world was indispensable for fostering world peace. It was during that summer that Rabindranath met several French scholars and artists and began to invite them to be part of his institution.

The Orientalist Sylvain Levi (1863-1935) a professor at the University of Sorbonne was one of the first scholars that Rabindranath met and invited. In his diary, Rathindranath Tagore,

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who along with his wife Pratima, had accompanied his father on this trip to Europe (and later to America) recalls that Levi came to meet his father; Rathindranath described the scholar as a ‘charming man’ who was both ‘unassuming’ and ‘genial.’¹⁶ His students who were devoted to him referred to him as ‘Mahaguru’, which translates as the great master-teacher. The appellation was apt because Levi, who had studied Sanskrit for six years at Sorbonne and succeeded his teacher Abel Bergaigne to the chair, learned Chinese and Tibetan soon after with the intention of pursuing Buddhist studies. By 1894 Levi had begun a life-long collaboration with the scholar Chavanna.¹⁷ With his expertise in both Hindu and Buddhist textual cultures, Sylvain Levi fulfilled Rabindranath’s ideal of the scholar who could initiate Indological studies in Visva-Bharati. Soon after he had secured a promise from Sylvain Levi, Rabindranath travelled to Prague where he met the Jewish Austrian scholar Moriz Winternitz (1863-1937), a Professor of Sanskrit at Karl-Ferdinands-Universität, Prague. Winternitz who had long admired Rabindranath’s poetry was impressed with the poet and his idea of Visva-Bharati and agreed to be part of its program of Indology.

On November 10, 1921, the renowned French scholar Sylvain Levi and his wife Desiree Sylvain Levi arrived in Santiniketan on the invitation of Rabindranath Tagore who had met them in Paris about six months earlier. Rabindranath had requested the famous savant to be part of his project of Visva-Bharati, a world centre of learning and culture, whose foundations he had laid three years back in this quiet, rural settlement in Bengal. Sylvain Levi began his teaching career at Sorbonne, where he taught Sanskrit having completed his doctoral dissertation on ‘The Indian Theatre.’ At the time Rabindranath met him, Levi was a Professor at the very prestigious College de France where he had been teaching since 1894. That this very senior and ageing academic set aside an offer to deliver lectures at Harvard to accept the post of the first visiting professor at Visva-Bharati is a clear sign of his faith in Rabindranath Tagore who was well-known among the global fraternity of

intellectuals. The other foreigners who had responded to Rabindranath's call to give shape to his dream of Visva-Bharati were Leonard Knight Elmhirst, a young Englishman pursuing a course in agricultural science at Cornell and Stella Kramrisch, a Viennese art historian. Rabindranath had heard about Leonard Elmhirst from common friends – Sam Higginbottom and Harriet Moody. He was keen that the young Englishman who had a desire to work in Indian villages, accompany him to Santiniketan where he had been planning a full-scale village development project in the nearby village of Surul. With Stella Kramrisch it was a chance meeting in an academic gathering. Rabindranath, impressed with her lecture, invited her to the newly established Kala-Bhavana or the centre of fine arts and music. These invited guests had arrived by early December 1921 and were acclimatizing themselves to the place and its ethos. According to Madame Levi's diary, her husband began to take classes soon after he arrived. There were daily Sanskrit classes and on Sundays, lectures on Buddhist literary texts, and religious treatises. Teachers and Ceylonese Buddhist monks of the Santiniketan ashram attended these classes.¹⁸

A formal inauguration: the public announcement about Visva-Bharati

Rabindranath had chosen the 8th day of Poush, 22 December 1921, for the first session of the Visva-Bharati parishat, the highest council of the institution. Since it was a ceremony attended not only by the 'foreign' visitors but also distinguished guests from Calcutta, it has become customary to regard this as the formal inauguration of the institution, though its foundation had been laid three years back on the very same date. Exactly two decades earlier, Rabindranath had founded the ashram school on the 7th day of Poush which carried a special significance for the Santiniketan ashram community. The reasons for this lay in the Brahmo origins of the ashram, which was originally conceived of as a retreat for the members of the faith.

Rabindranath's father Debendranath Tagore, who had originally

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bought the land – which he named as Santiniketan, had converted to Brahma faith, a monotheistic religion which drew upon the Upanishads, on the 7th day of Poush. Consequently, this day and those following acquired a holy/ auspicious association and were marked by a series of cultural events linked to the institution, and the community. One of these was a special prayer meeting held in the Mandir or a prayer hall, one of the first constructions in the ashram. A magnificent stained-glass edifice mounted on cast iron, the Mandir was not a temple of worship in the received sense of the term. In keeping with the tenets of Brahma religion, the Mandir did not have an idol or shrine; the large hall was meant for prayer-meetings, presided over by an *acharya*. Typically, the *acharya* explicated on some spiritual or ethical issue that had its roots in the Upanishad and was linked to the principles of the ashram. When Rabindranath was present in Santiniketan, he performed the role of the *acharya*.

A ceremony took place in the amra-kunja or mango-grove of the Santiniketan ashram on 23 December 1921 during which Rabindranath Tagore extended a warm welcome to the distinguished guests – the philosopher Brajendranath Seal, the Indologist Sylvan Levi and his wife Madame Levi. Also present were two renowned physicians from Calcutta – Dr Nilratan Sircar and Sisir kumar Maitra and the teachers and scholars of the Santiniketan ashram and other invited foreign guests.¹⁹ Rabindranath paid a special homage to Sylvan Levi, stating that it was a matter of great good fortune that the renowned scholar was present as a ‘representative of the West’ in the first/inaugural session which marked ‘Visva-Bharati’s engagement with the ‘visva’ [world].’²⁰

Rabindranath requested Brajendranath Seal (1864-1938), a renowned educationist and humanist philosopher, for whom he had great respect and admiration, to preside over the session. Like many late 19th century thinkers, Brajendranath Seal’s early philosophical work was deeply influenced by the Positivism of August Comte; Seal also visited Europe in 1899, 1906, 1911 and addressed the International Congress of Orientalists in Rome (1911). Lavishing

praise on the philosopher as one who had seen the world of learning with his liberal and empathetic vision, Rabindranath stressed that Brajendranath possessed the remarkable ability to perceive a unity in the various and wide-ranging fields of knowledge.²¹

In the beginning of his long address, Brajendranath Seal dwelt on the significance of the name of the institution. He pointed out that lexically, Visva-Bharati, meant, ‘bharati [the goddess of learning or Saraswati, part of the Hindu pantheon of deities] who had been working unseen now made herself visible to the world or *visva*.’ But, he added that the term also suggested the arrival of *visva* in *bharat* [India]; by making this world its own, the country would then return it as a gift to mankind²² [translation mine]. Throughout this address delivered on 23 December 1921, Rabindranath alluded several times to *visva* or the world. The emphasis was on the role of Visva-Bharati the institution, in facilitating a mutually enriching relation between the home and the world. By announcing the ideal or aspiration of Viva-Bharati as a world centre of learning and Santiniketan as a hospitable habitation for a community across the globe, the founder conferred an international status to his institution.²³ The announcement of the international stature of Visva-Bharati was not merely a poet’s dream but a reality made possible by the coming of several European Orientalists to Santiniketan to be part of Visva-Bharati.

European scholars in Santiniketan

In December 1922, Winternitz came to Santiniketan with his student Vincent Lesney. Though he stayed only for nine months, this was a fruitful exchange; Winternitz continued his work on the translation of *Mahabharata* and also had long discussions about editing with his ten students. The most valuable addition to this group was Ananta Sastri, a former faculty of the Bhandarkar Institute of Baroda. It was primarily through Sastri’s untiring effort that a collection of Sanskrit manuscripts of the *Mahabharata* was made possible. Winternitz, like Levi, did not stay for long. In his farewell

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address, on the occasion of Winternitz's departure from Santiniketan, Rabindranath felt it important to point out that it was not the duration of the stay that mattered but the impact, 'though in outward appearance the time of your stay with us has been short, spiritually it has acquired a permanence in our hearts.'²⁴ The founder of the institution remarked that Winternitz was a scholar free from 'race prejudice' and the 'narrow spirit of national egotism' whose presence in Santiniketan was a 'living contribution to the building' of Visva-Bharati.²⁵ He reiterated his faith in the process of the building of the institution through a 'ceaseless endeavor to reach the highest expression of the spiritual meaning of existence.'²⁶

Among the scholars who came after Winternitz was the Norwegian Orientalist Sten Konow (1867-1948).²⁷ Konow's special field was study of Sanskrit and linguistics and he had held many important positions in prestigious universities. In the summer of 1920, when Rabindranath was touring Europe, Konow invited him to Oslo. Though Rabindranath could not go, he continued to correspond with Konow. Typically, the founder of Visva-Bharati wanted the scholar to be part of the project of Oriental research that he had established in his newly established institution. Konow accepted the offer and was to be paid a remuneration of Rs 500 – a royal sum in those days, especially given the acute financial crunch that the institution had. The Konow couple arrived in the winter of 1924 and stayed till the spring of 1925. They soon became part of the Santiniketan community, enjoying the Poush mela and a fair at nearby Kenduli. As a scholar Konow delivered a couple of public lectures on themes like the evolution of the Indian religions, the study of Tibetan Buddhist texts with special focus on the Dhammapada. The historian Kalidas Nag and the linguist Sunitikumar Chattopadhyay came from Calcutta to attend his lectures. Though Sten Konow's sojourn in Santiniketan was brief, the bond between the Orientalist scholar and the poet from the Orient was strong.

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In 1925, two Italian Orientalist scholars, Carlo Formici (1871-1943) and Guiseppe Tucci (1895-1984) came to Visva-Bharati as part of an unstated political mission. Benito Mussolini (1883-1945), the country's fascist premier, who was trying to win Rabindranath's support, sent as gifts invaluable books on Italian art and aesthetics; he also decided to finance the visit and stay of these two scholars. In his short essay written for the Tagore Centenary volume, Tucci recalled that he came to Santiniketan in November 1925. He had been sent by the Italian Government to introduce the study of Italian language. It was a matter of felicity that he did not limit himself to the brief given by the government but 'collaborated with the many Indian scholars assembled there in various fields of Oriental studies, chiefly Tibetan and Chinese.'²⁸ Tucci provides a succinct account of the orientation of research studies in Visva-Bharati:

Buddhism received great attention in the curriculum of studies in Santiniketan. Tibetan and Chinese were there given the same importance as Sanskrit, because he [Rabindranath] was quite aware that there was a greater India, where the most brilliant and everlasting conquests of her thinkers had spread their inspiration. At that time, Santiniketan was perhaps the only place in India, where one could pursue comparative researches in Buddhism, because there one was able not only to meet Chinese and Tibetan scholars, or to discuss with the most learned pundits, but could also find books not available elsewhere.

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It would thus not be an exaggeration to state that between December 1921 and November 1926, Visva-Bharati seemed to have lived up to its motto of becoming a nest for the world.

Foreign scholars and the ideal of hospitality in Visva-Bharati

The scholars who Rabindranath invited in the inaugural phase of the Indological/Oriental studies in Visva-Bharati were, without exception, Europeans. Did this imply that he had felt a lack of excellence in the field in India? It is not likely that Rabindranath was

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unaware of the work of senior pundits like Haraprasad Sashtri, Brajendranath Seal, Pramathanath Tarkabhushan. The younger lot included Ramaprasad Chanda of the University of Calcutta and Kashiprasad Jaisawal of Patna. There were others like Ganganath Jha of Allahabad, the archaeologist Rakhaldas Bandopadhyay and Pandurang Baman Kane. It has been argued that though scholars like Kalidas Nag, Radhakamal and Radhakumud Mukhopadhyay and Jahangir Taraporewala, came briefly to deliver lectures in Visva-Bharati, none of these stalwarts were ever given the status that Rabindranath had accorded to the foreigners.

It is possible to argue that Rabindranath viewed the Orientalists / Indologists from Europe as guests, not only of his institution but also of the country. He had long believed that hospitality was integral to the ethos of the country, an idea that he had explored in the essay 'Bharatbarsher Itihaash'³⁰ (1902) [A History of Bharatbarsha]. The reason why the Sanskrit phrase *yatra visvam bhabatye ekaneedam* (where the world makes home in a nest) appealed to him as the motto of the institution is because he believed that it was possible to turn the Santiniketan ashram to a hospitable habitation for scholars, scientists, and artists, across the world. This, he believed was one, perhaps the only, resistance to powerful systems – in the form of colonialism, capitalism and nationalism which were trampling over all that was worth cherishing in human existence. In the lecture titled "Guest House of India" he spoke eloquently of how in India, the *grihastha* or householder regarded himself as fortunate if the guest came to his door; pointing to the scriptural articulation *atithi devobhava* Rabindranath stressed that the status of the guest was equivalent to that of the god.³¹ Addressing his foreign audience he said that it was necessary to take this cherished principle of his ancestors into the contemporary times so that modern India can make provisions of hospitality for the seekers from other lands. He provided the instance of the ancient Indian universities of Nalanda and Takshasila 'where students used to come from China, from Western Asia and even from Europe.'³² He

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hoped that Visva-Bharati would be able to revive this tradition and build anew this spirit of hospitality.

For Rabindranath hospitality was not a one-way process of giving but also a process of gaining. It involved an active exchange between the host and the guest. Rabindranath projected Visva-Bharati especially with its focus on Asian comparative studies as a centre for an initiation of this dialogue. The invitation to Sylvain Levi and later other European Orientalists to Visva-Bharati was to initiate this exchange between the scholars of Asia and Europe. For the first time since colonial modernity, Westerners had come at the behest of an Indian to be part of his project of creating a world centre of learning and culture. This in itself over-turned the hegemonic model in which the West determined the production of knowledge and modes of its dissemination. By foregrounding the presence of Western scholars at the inaugural moment of Visva-Bharati, Rabindranath wanted the world to take cognizance that such a non-hierarchized exchange was possible.

One instance of this was the exchange with the scholars of the Bhandarkar Institute founded by the students and colleagues of Ramakrishna Gopal Bhandarkar, the legendary Indian scholar of Sanskrit and Oriental studies. It was Bhandarkar's admirers and disciples who took the initiative to set up the institution on the occasion of the savant's 80th birthday in Pune in 1917. A major asset of the institute was the valuable and rare ancient religious texts and manuscripts, in Sanskrit, Pali and Prakrit most of which came from Bhandarkar's own collection. The institute began to bring out its scholarly research journal, *The Bhandarkar Annals* soon after its inception. One of the major works undertaken by the Bhandarkar institute was the critical edition of the Mahabharata. It was during the visit of Moriz Winternitz that a very important work of collation and collaboration between the two centres in Pune and Santiniketan took place. Thus, it is clear that the 'foreign' scholars in Visva-Bharati were not working in any insularity but in tandem with the Orientalist scholars in India. This was the closest the Visva-

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Bharati came to realizing one of the major objects of the Constitution viz. ‘To seek to realise in a common fellowship of study the meeting of East and West, and thus ultimately to strengthen the fundamental conditions of world peace through the establishment of free communication of ideas between the two hemispheres.’ A “free communication” implied a non-hierarchical relation/exchange between Asia and Europe and this could be achieved by re-conceptualizing the East, one that would allow it to be free from the damaging stereotypes of dominant discourses of the West. That such an exchange between the East and West had been possible, within the framework of an institution of culture and learning, located in an idyllic ashram campus in Santiniketan is an amazing achievement, one that bears testimony to Rabindranath’s ability to make his dreams come true.

Endnotes :

¹ Rabindranath Tagore, ‘The Message of the Forest’ in Sisir Kumar Das, ed. *The English Writings of Rabindranath Tagore* (New Delhi: Sahitya Akademi, 1996), vol. II, 383-400, p. 393.

² Rabindranath Thakur, ‘Siksha’ translated and quoted by Himangshu Bhushan Mukherjee, *Education for Fullness: A Study of the Educational Thought and Experiment of Rabindranath Tagore* (New Delhi : Routledge, 2013), p.35.

³ Rabindranath Thakur, ‘Sikshar Samasya’ *Siksha* (Kolkata: Visva-Bharati BS 1342), p 56.

⁴ Sabyasachi Bhattacharys, ed. *The Poet and the Mahatma* (New Delhi: National Book Trust, 1997), p. 50.

⁵ These were later published as three essays in the collection *Nationalism* (London: Macmillan, 1917).

⁶ Rabindranath Tagore, *Letters to Rathindranath Tagore*, vol. 2, ed. Supriya Roy (Kolkata: Visva-Bharati, 2012), p. 70.

⁷ Tagore, *Letters to Rathindranath Tagore*, p.70.

⁸ Excerpt from a letter written by Rathindranath Tagore to Mrs Seymour on 30th March 1921. *Rabindra biksha* 48: p. 40.

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- ⁹ H.B. Mukherjee, *Education for Fullness* (New Delhi: Routledge, 2011), pp.70-71.
- ¹⁰ Rabindranath Tagore, *Visva-Bharati* (Kolkata: Visva-Bharati, BS 1358), Lecture I, p. 7.
- ¹¹ Tagore, Visva-Bharati Lecture I, p.8.
- ¹² Tagore, Visva-Bharati Lecture I, p.8.
- ¹³ Tagore, Visva-Bharati Lecture I, p.9.
- ¹⁴ Tagore, Visva-Bharati Lecture I, pp. 9-10.
- ¹⁵ Tagore, Visva-Bharati Lecture I, p.10
- ¹⁶ *The Diaries of Rathindranath Tagore*, ed. Supriya Roy (Kolkata: Karigar, 2013), p.99.
- ¹⁷ http://himalaya.socanth.cam.ac.uk/collections/journals/kailash/pdf/kailash_03_01_01.pdf. Accessed 10.5.17.
- ¹⁸ *Madam Levir Diary*, trans. and ed. Nandadulal Dey (Kolkata : Ananda Publishers, 2000), p. 7.
- ¹⁹ The list of teachers included the Sanskrit pundit Vidushekhara Sastri, Haricharan Bandyopadhyay, Kshitimohan Sen, Jagadananda Ray, Nepalchandra Ray all of who taught in the ashram school. The artists Nandalal Bose, Surendranath Kar and Asitkumar Halder were part of Kala-Bhavana. CF Andrews and William Pearson were involved in the Santiniketan ashram community in manifold ways. Hidjibhai Pestonji Morris, a Parsi, taught French.
- ²⁰ Rabindranath Tagore, *Visva-Bharati*, Lecture III, pp. 20-21.
- ²¹ Tagore, Visva-Bharati, Lecture III, p.21.
- ²² Prasanta Pal, *Rabijiboni*, vol. ix (Kolkata: Ananda Publishers, 2001), p. 165. The entire lecture is appended to the lecture series, Visva-Bharati, pp. 159-168.
- ²³ This motto would be encapsulated through the Sanskrit phrase, '*yatra visvambhatyate ekaneedam*' derived from the Upanishads, which translates as 'where the world makes its home in a nest.'
- ²⁴ Rabindranath Tagore, 'Farewell to Dr. M. Winternitz' in Sisir Kumar Das ed. *The English Writings of Rabindranath Tagore*, vol. iii, pp. 759-60; 760.
- ²⁵ Das, *The English Writings of Rabindranath Tagore*, vol. iii, p.760.
- ²⁶ Das, *The English Writings of Rabindranath Tagore*, vol. iii, p. 760.

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and European Orientalist scholars

²⁷ Trained originally in the European classical languages and Old Norse, Sten Konow later learnt Sanskrit from a well known German scholar.

²⁸ Giuseppe Tucci, 'Recollections of Tagore' in *Rabindranath Tagore, A Centenary Volume 1861-1961* (New Delhi: Sahitya Akademi, 1961), pp. 59-60; 59.

²⁹ *Rabindranath Tagore, A Centenary Volume 1861-1961*, pp. 59-60.

³⁰ Rabindranath Thakur, 'Bharatbarsher Itihash' in *Itihash* [compiled by Prabodh chandra Sen and Pulinbihari Sen] (Kolkata: Visva-Bharati, BS1420), pp.5-15. The 'authentic' history of Bharatbarsha, Rabindranath suggests, is in the lives of the ordinary people who have not succumbed to the onslaught of various invasions and regimes but have thrived by drawing sustenance from its own resources. Unlike Europe which has had to impose an external political unity on elements that are diverse and opposing, Bharatbarsha, has tried to forge unity by establishing relationships of affect with that which is genuinely contrary to the self. Thus, Europe needs to exercise constant control to ensure that the 'other' does not become powerful; Bharatbarsha, on the other hand, has tried to achieve unity by respecting the 'other' and allowing it to retain its distinctiveness.

³¹ Rabindranath Tagore, 'The Guest House of India' in Nityapriya Ghosh ed. *The English Writings of Rabindranath Tagore* (New Delhi: Sahitya Akademi, 2007) vol. iv, pp. 485-487.

³² Tagore, 'The Guest House of India' *The English Writings of Rabindranath Tagore* ed. Nityapriya Ghosh vol. iv, p. 486.